

BACKGROUND/TASK-SPECIFIC QUESTIONS

1. Do you have reading difficulty?
A: Yes B: NO
2. What's your gender?
A: Male B: Female
3. Which year do you enroll in university(undergraduate)?
4. How many years have you been programming?
5. How many related programming courses did you complete?
6. How did you estimate your Java programming experience (scale:1-5, 1 means least best and 5 means best)?
7. How did you estimate your other programming experience (scale:1-5, 1 means least best and 5 means best)?
8. How did you estimate your Java programming experience compare to your classmates (scale:1-5, 1 means least best and 5 means best)?
9. How many lines of code have you programed?
A: Less than 900 lines B: More than 900 and less than 40000 C: More than 40000
10. Which naming conventions do you prefer? under_score(like sold_card) or camelCase(like soldCard)?
A: I prefer under_score style B: I prefer camelCase style C: I have no preference
11. How Do you level your competence of principles of object-oriented design? (scale 1-5. 1 means no competence and 5 means expert level competence)
12. How Do you level your competence of model design? (scale 1-5. 1 means no competence and 5 means expert level competence)
13. How Do you level your competence of code smell and refactoring? (scale 1-5. 1 means no competence and 5 means expert level competence)
14. How Do you level your competence of programming Eclipse plug-ins? (scale 1-5. 1 means no competence and 5 means expert level competence)

CODE SNIPPETS

Code snippet 1_1 (With duplicated code)

```
/**
 * Checks if a square has a pit. Returns false
 * if the position is invalid, or if the square is
 * unknown.
 *
 * @param x X position
 * @param y Y position
 * @return True if the square has a pit
 */
public boolean hasPit(int x, int y)
{
    if (!isValidPosition(x,y)) return false;
}
```

```

    if (isUnknown(x,y)) return false;
    if (w[x][y].contains(PIT))
        return true;
    else
        return false;
}

//Checks if the Wumpus is in a square.
public boolean hasWumpus(int x, int y)
{
    if (!isValidPosition(x,y)) return false;
    if (isUnknown(x,y)) return false;
    if (w[x][y].contains(WUMPUS))
        return true;
    else
        return false;
}

//Checks if a square is valid.
public boolean isValidPosition(int x, int y)
{
    if (x < 1) return false;
    if (y < 1) return false;
    if (x > size) return false;
    if (y > size) return false;
    return true;
}

//Checks if a square is unknown.
public boolean isUnknown(int x, int y)
{
    if (!isValidPosition(x,y)) return false;
    if (w[x][y].contains(UNKNOWN))
        return true;
    else
        return false;
}

```

Code snippet 1_2 (Non-duplicated code)

```

/**
 * Checks if a square has a pit. Returns false
 * if the position is invalid, or if the square is
 * unknown.
 *
 * @param x X position
 * @param y Y position
 * @return True if the square has a pit
 */
public boolean hasPit(int x, int y)
{
    if (!valid(x,y)) return false;
    if (w[x][y].contains(PIT))

```

```

        return true;
    else
        return false;
}

//Checks if the Wumpus is in a square.
public boolean hasWumpus(int x, int y)
{
    if (!valid(x,y)) return false;
    if (w[x][y].contains(WUMPUS))
        return true;
    else
        return false;
}

private boolean valid(int x, int y) {
    if (!isValidPosition(x,y)) return false;
    if (isUnknown(x,y)) return false;
    return true;
}

//Checks if a square is valid.
public boolean isValidPosition(int x, int y)
{
    if (x < 1) return false;
    if (y < 1) return false;
    if (x > size) return false;
    if (y > size) return false;
    return true;
}

//Checks if a square is unknown.
public boolean isUnknown(int x, int y)
{
    if (!isValidPosition(x,y)) return false;
    if (w[x][y].contains(UNKNOWN))
        return true;
    else
        return false;
}

```

Code snippet 2_1 (With duplicated code)

DayTest.java

```

//Test method GetFirstMillisecond() by creating Day type object
public void testGetFirstMillisecond() {
    Locale saved = Locale.getDefault();
    Locale.setDefault(Locale.UK);
    TimeZone savedZone = TimeZone.getDefault();
    TimeZone.setDefault(TimeZone.getTimeZone("Europe/London"));
    Day d = new Day(1,3,1970);
    assertEquals(5094000000L,d.getFirstMillisecond());
}

```

```
    Locale.setDefault(saved);
    TimeZone.setDefault(savedZone);
}
```

HourTest.java

```
//Test method GetFirstMillisecond() by creating Hour type object
public void testGetFirstMillisecond() {
    Locale saved = Locale.getDefault();
    Locale.setDefault(Locale.UK);
    TimeZone savedZone = TimeZone.getDefault();
    TimeZone.setDefault(TimeZone.getTimeZone("Europe/London"));
    Hour h = new Hour(15,1,4,2006);
    assertEquals(1143900000000L,h.getFirstMillisecond());
    Locale.setDefault(saved);
    TimeZone.setDefault(savedZone);
}
```

Code snippet 2_2 (Non-duplicated code)

```
public void extracted(RegularTimePeriod arg0,long arg1) {
    Locale saved = Locale.getDefault();
    Locale.setDefault(Locale.UK);
    TimeZone savedZone = TimeZone.getDefault();
    TimeZone.setDefault(TimeZone.getTimeZone("Europe/London"));
    RegularTimePeriod d = arg0;
    assertEquals(arg1,d.getFirstMillisecond());
    Locale.setDefault(saved);
    TimeZone.setDefault(savedZone);
}
```

```
//Test method GetFirstMillisecond() by creating Day type object
public void testGetFirstMillisecond() {
    extracted(new Day(1,3,1970),5094000000L);
}
```

```
//Test method GetFirstMillisecond() by creating Hour type object
public void testGetFirstMillisecond() {
    extracted(new Hour(15,1,4,2006),1143900000000L);
}
```

Code snippet 3_1 (With duplicated code)

LineContains.java

```
/**
* Returns the next character in the filtered stream, only including
* lines from the original stream which contain all of the specified words.
```

```

* @return the next character in the resulting stream, or -1
* if the end of the resulting stream has been reached
*/
public int read(){
    if(!getInitialized()) {
        initialize();
        setInitialized(true);
    }

    int ch = -1;
    if(line != null) {
        ch = line.charAt(0);
        if(line.length() == 1) {
            line = null;
        } else {
            line = line.substring(1);
        }
    } else {
        final int containsSize = contains.size();
        for(line = readLine(); line !=null; line = readLine()) {
            boolean matches = true;
            for(int i=0; matches && i<containsSize; i++) {
                String containsStr = (String)contains.elementAt(i);
                matches = line.indexOf(containsStr)>=0;
            }
            if(matches^isNegated()) {
                break;
            }
        }
        if(line != null) {
            return read();
        }
    }
    return ch;
}

```

LineContainsRegExp.java

```

/**
* Returns the next character in the filtered stream, only including
* lines from the original stream which match all of the specified
* regular expressions.
* @return the next character in the resulting stream, or -1
* if the end of the resulting stream has been reached
*/
public int read(){
    if(!getInitialized()) {
        initialize();
        setInitialized(true);
    }

    int ch = -1;
    if(line != null) {

```

```

    ch = line.charAt(0);
    if(line.length() == 1) {
        line = null;
    } else {
        line = line.substring(1);
    }
} else {
    final int containsSize = contains.size();
    for(line = readLine(); line != null; line = readLine()) {
        boolean matches = true;
        for(int i=0; matches && i<regexpsSize; i++) {
            RegularExpression regexp
                =(RegularExpression)regexps.elementAt(i);
            Regexp re = regexp.getRegexp(getProject());
            matches = re.matches(line);
        }
        if(matches^isNegated()) {
            break;
        }
    }
    if(line != null) {
        return read();
    }
}
return ch;
}

```

Code snippet 3_2 (Non-duplicated code)

```

/**
 * Returns the next character in the filtered stream, only including
 * lines from the original stream which match all of the specified
 * regular expressions or contain all of the specified words.
 *
 * @return the next character in the resulting stream, or -1
 * if the end of the resulting stream has been reached
 */
public int extracted(Vector vector, Function<Integer, Boolean> matcher){
    if(!getInitialized()) {
        initialize();
        setInitialized(true);
    }

    int ch = -1;
    if(line != null) {
        ch = line.charAt(0);
        if(line.length() == 1) {
            line = null;
        } else {
            line = line.substring(1);
        }
    }
} else {

```

```

    final int containsSize = vector.size();
    for(line = readLine(); line != null; line = readLine()) {
        boolean matches = true;
        for(int i=0; matches && i<containsSize; i++) {
            matches = (boolean)matcher.apply(i);
        }
        if(matches^isNegated()) {
            break;
        }
    }
    if(line != null) {
        return read();
    }
}
return ch;
}

```

LineContains.java

```

public int read(){
    return extracted(contains,
        (Integer i) -> {
            String containsStr = (String)contains.elementAt(i);
            return line.indexOf(containsStr)>=0;
        }
    );
}

```

LineContainsRegExp.java

```

public int read(){
    return extracted(regexps,
        (Integer i) -> {
            RegularExpression regexp =
                (RegularExpression)regexps.elementAt(i);
            Regexp re = regexp.getRegexp(getProject());
            return re.matches(line);
        }
    );
}

```

Code snippet 1_1 (With duplicated code)

```

/**
 * Checks if a square has a pit. Returns false
 * if the position is invalid, or if the square is
 * unknown.
 *
 * @param x X position
 * @param y Y position
 * @return True if the square has a pit
 */
public boolean hasPit(int x, int y)
{

```

```

    if (!A:_____) return false;
    if (isUnknown(x,y)) return false;
    if (w[x][y].contains(PIT))
        return true;
    else
        return false;
}

//Checks if the Wumpus is in a square.
public boolean hasWumpus(int x, int y)
{
    if (!B:_____) return false;
    if (isUnknown(x,y)) return false;
    if (w[x][y].contains(WUMPUS))
        return true;
    else
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}

//Checks if a square is valid.
public boolean isValidPosition(int x, int y)
{
    if (x < 1) return false;
    if (y < 1) return false;
    if (x > size) return false;
    if (y > size) return false;
    return true;
}

//Checks if a square is unknown.
public boolean isUnknown(int x, int y)
{
    if (!isValidPosition(x,y)) return false;
    if C:_____.contains(UNKNOWN))
        return true;
    else
        return false;
}

```

Code snippet 1_2 (Non-duplicated code)

```

/**
 * Checks if a square has a pit. Returns false
 * if the position is invalid, or if the square is
 * unknown.
 *
 * @param x X position
 * @param y Y position
 * @return True if the square has a pit
 */
public boolean hasPit(int x, int y)
{
    if (!A:_____) return false;

```

```

    if (w[x][y].contains(PIT))
        return true;
    else
        return false;
}

//Checks if the Wumpus is in a square.
public boolean hasWumpus(int x, int y)
{
    if (!B:_____) return false;
    if (w[x][y].contains(WUMPUS))
        return true;
    else
        return false;
}

private boolean valid(int x, int y) {
    if (!isValidPosition(x,y)) return false;
    if (isUnknown(x,y)) return false;
    return true;
}

//Checks if a square is valid.
public boolean isValidPosition(int x, int y)
{
    if (x < 1) return false;
    if (y < 1) return false;
    if (x > size) return false;
    if (y > size) return false;
    return true;
}

//Checks if a square is unknown.
public boolean isUnknown(int x, int y)
{
    if (!isValidPosition(x,y)) return false;
    if (C:_____.contains(UNKNOWN))
        return true;
    else
        return false;
}

```

Code snippet 2_1 (With duplicated code)

DayTest.java

```

//Test method GetFirstMillisecond() by creating Day type object
public void testGetFirstMillisecond() {
    Locale saved = Locale.getDefault();
    Locale.setDefault(Locale.UK);
    TimeZone savedZone = TimeZone.getDefault();
    TimeZone.setDefault(TimeZone.getTimeZone("Europe/London"));
    Day d = new Day(1,3,1970);
}

```

```

    assertEquals(5094000000L,A:_____.getFirstMillisecond());
    Locale.setDefault(B:_____);
    TimeZone.setDefault(savedZone);
}

```

HourTest.java

```

//Test method GetFirstMillisecond() by creating Hour type object
public void testGetFirstMillisecond() {
    Locale saved = Locale.getDefault();
    Locale.setDefault(Locale.UK);
    TimeZone savedZone = TimeZone.getDefault();
    TimeZone.setDefault(TimeZone.getTimeZone("Europe/London"));
    Hour h = new Hour(15,1,4,2006);
    assertEquals(1143900000000L,h.getFirstMillisecond());
    Locale.setDefault(saved);
    TimeZone.setDefault(C:_____);
}

```

Code snippet 2_2 (Non-duplicated code)

```

public void extracted(RegularTimePeriod arg0,long arg1) {
    Locale saved = Locale.getDefault();
    Locale.setDefault(Locale.UK);
    TimeZone savedZone = TimeZone.getDefault();
    TimeZone.setDefault(TimeZone.getTimeZone("Europe/London"));
    RegularTimePeriod d = arg0;
    assertEquals(arg1,d.getFirstMillisecond());
    Locale.setDefault(A:_____);
    TimeZone.setDefault(B:_____);
}

```

```

//Test method GetFirstMillisecond() by creating Day type object
public void testGetFirstMillisecond() {
    extracted(new C:_____(1,3,1970),5094000000L);
}

```

```

//Test method GetFirstMillisecond() by creating Hour type object
public void testGetFirstMillisecond() {
    extracted(new Hour(15,1,4,2006),1143900000000L);
}

```

Code snippet 3_1 (With duplicated code)

LineContains.java

```

/**
 * Returns the next character in the filtered stream, only including

```

```

* lines from the original stream which contain all of the specified words.
* @return the next character in the resulting stream, or -1
* if the end of the resulting stream has been reached
*/
public int read(){
    if(!getInitialized()) {
        initialize();
        setInitialized(true);
    }

    int ch = -1;
    if(line != null) {
        ch = line.charAt(0);
        if(line.length() == 1) {
            line = null;
        } else {
            line = line.substring(1);
        }
    } else {
        final int containsSize = contains.size();
        for(line = readLine(); line != A:_____ ; line = readLine()) {
            boolean matches = true;
            for(int i=0; matches && i<containsSize; i++) {
                String containsStr = (String)contains.elementAt(i);
                matches = line.indexOf(B:_____)>=0;
            }
            if(matches^isNegated()) {
                break;
            }
        }
        if(line != null) {
            return read();
        }
    }
    return D:_____ ;
}

```

LineContainsRegExp.java

```

/**
* Returns the next character in the filtered stream, only including
* lines from the original stream which match all of the specified
* regular expressions.
* @return the next character in the resulting stream, or -1
* if the end of the resulting stream has been reached
*/
public int read(){
    if(!getInitialized()) {
        initialize();
        setInitialized(true);
    }

    int ch = -1;

```

```

if(line != null) {
    ch = line.charAt(0);
    if(line.length() == 1) {
        line = null;
    } else {
        line = line.substring(1);
    }
} else {
    final int containsSize = contains.size();
    for(line = readLine(); line != A:____; line = readLine()) {
        boolean matches = true;
        for(int i=0; matches && i<regexpsSize; i++) {
            RegularExpression regexp
                =(RegularExpression)regexps.elementAt(i);
            Regexp re = C:____.getRegexp(getProject());
            matches = re.matches(line);
        }
        if(matches^isNegated()) {
            break;
        }
    }
    if(line != null) {
        return read();
    }
}
return D:____;
}

```

Code snippet 3_2 (Non-duplicated code)

```

/**
 * Returns the next character in the filtered stream, only including
 * lines from the original stream which match all of the specified
 * regular expressions or contain all of the specified words.
 *
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 */
public int extracted(Vector vector, Function<Integer, Boolean> matcher){
    if(!getInitialized()) {
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        setInitialized(true);
    }

    int ch = -1;
    if(line != null) {
        ch = line.charAt(0);
        if(line.length() == 1) {
            line = null;
        } else {
            line = line.substring(1);
        }
    }
}

```

```

    }
} else {
    final int containsSize = vector.size();
    for(line = readLine(); line != A:_____ ; line = readLine()) {
        boolean matches = true;
        for(int i=0; matches && i<containsSize; i++) {
            matches = (boolean)matcher.apply(i);
        }
        if(matches^isNegated()) {
            break;
        }
    }
    if(line != null) {
        return read();
    }
}
return B:_____ ;
}

```

LineContains.java

```

public int read(){
    return extracted(contains ,
        (Integer i) -> {
            String containsStr = (String)contains.elementAt(i);
            return line.indexOf(C:_____)>=0;
        }
    );
}

```

LineContainsRegExp.java

```

public int read(){
    return extracted(regexps ,
        (Integer i) -> {
            RegularExpression regexp =
                (RegularExpression)regexps.elementAt(i);
            Regexp re = D:_____.getRegexp(getProject());
            return re.matches(line);
        }
    );
}

```